

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Google Earth Engine asosida suv omborlari monitoringi (Talimarjon suv ombori misolida)

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada Google Earth Engine (GEE) platformasi asosida suv omborlarining masofadan monitoringini amalga oshirish hamda suv yuzasi va suv hajmi o'rtasidagi bog'lanishni baholash masalalari tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqot obyekti sifatida Talimarjon suv ombori tanlandi. Sentinel-1 SAR va Landsat sun'iy yo'ldosh ma'lumotlari asosida suvli yuzalar aniqlanib, vaqt qatorlari shakllantirildi. SAR tasvirlaridan foydalanish bulutlilik muammosini bartaraf etish imkonini berdi va suv yuzasini aniqlash aniqligini oshirdi. Suv yuzasining o'zgarishi va suv hajmi o'rtasidagi bog'lanishni aniqlash maqsadida 2023 va 2025 yillarda o'tkazilgan batimetrik o'lchash natijalari asosida regressiya modellar tuzildi. Chiziqli va darajali regressiya modellari tahlil qilinib, yuqori aniqlik ko'rsatkichlariga ($R^2 = 0,98 - 0,99$) erishildi. Olingan bog'lanish tenglamalari asosida suv hajmi va suv sathi balandligining oylik qiymatlari hisoblandi hamda ularning vaqt bo'yicha o'zgarish tendensiyalari tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqot natijalari Google Earth Engine platformasidan foydalanib suv omborlari holatini muntazam kuzatish, suv resurslarini baholash va boshqarish jarayonlarida amaliy ahamiyatga ega ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Google Earth Engine, masofadan zondlash, suv ombori, Sentinel-1, SAR, suv yuzasi, suv hajmi, regressiya modeli.

1. Kirish

Suv resurslarini samarali boshqarish va ularning holatini doimiy monitoring qilish global iqlim o'zgarishi, aholi sonining o'sishi hamda suvga bo'lgan talabning ortishi sharoitida dolzarb vazifalardan biri hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, sun'iy suv omborlarining suv sathi, suvli yuzasi va suv hajmining vaqt bo'yicha o'zgarishini aniq baholash gidrotexnik inshootlardan oqilona foydalanish va xavflarni kamaytirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. So'nggi yillarda masofadan zondlash texnologiyalari va sun'iy yo'ldosh ma'lumotlari asosida suv havzalarini monitoring qilish usullari keng qo'llanilmoqda. Bu yo'nalishda katta hajmdagi geofazoviy ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash imkoniyatiga ega bo'lgan Google Earth Engine (GEE) platformasi alohida ahamiyatga ega. U global sun'iy yo'ldosh ma'lumotlar bazalari bilan ishlash, fazoviy-vaqt qatorlarini tahlil qilish hamda hisoblash jarayonlarini yuqori aniqlikda amalga oshirish imkonini beradi.

Suv omborlarini monitoring qilishda asosiy muammolardan biri — bulutlilik ta'siri va ma'lumotlarning uzluksiz emasligidir. Ushbu muammoni hal etishda radar tasvirlariga asoslangan Sentinel-1 sun'iy yo'ldosh ma'lumotlaridan foydalanish samarali hisoblanadi. SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) texnologiyasi orqali olingan tasvirlar bulutli va yog'ingarchilik sharoitida ham suv yuzasini aniqlash imkonini beradi.

Mazkur tadqiqotda Google Earth Engine platformasi asosida Talimarjon suv omborining suv yuzasini masofadan turib aniqlash, uning vaqt bo'yicha o'zgarishini tahlil qilish hamda suv yuzasi va suv hajmi o'rtasidagi bog'lanishni regressiya modellari yordamida baholash maqsad qilib olingan. Olingan natijalar suv resurslarini baholash va boshqarish tizimlarini takomillashtirishda amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

2.Masalaning qo'yilishi

Suv havzalarini masofadan monitoring qilish masalalari ko'plab tadqiqotlarda ko'rib chiqilgan. Ilmiy adabiyotlarda sun'iy yo'ldosh tasvirlari asosida suv yuzasini aniqlash uchun spektral indekslar, tasvirlarni tasniflash va porog usullari keng qo'llaniladi. Ayniqsa, Landsat va Sentinel sun'iy yo'ldoshlari ma'lumotlari suv obyektlarini kuzatishda asosiy manbalar hisoblanadi.

Optik diapazonda olingan tasvirlar asosida suv obyektlarini aniqlashda NDWI, MNDWI kabi suv indekslaridan foydalanish keng tarqalgan. Biroq, bunday usullar bulutlilik va yorug'lik sharoitlariga bog'liq bo'lib, ma'lumotlarning uzluksizligini ta'minlashda cheklovlarga ega. Shu sababli, so'nggi yillarda SAR texnologiyalariga asoslangan tadqiqotlar soni ortmoqda.

Sentinel-1 sun'iy yo'ldoshi ma'lumotlari asosida suv yuzasini aniqlashda orqaga tarqalish koeffitsientlaridan foydalanish samarali usul sifatida qayd etilgan. Ilmiy ishlarda suv yuzasi odatda past tarqalish qiymatlari bilan xarakterlanishi va quruqlik fonida aniq ajralib turishi ta'kidlanadi. Bu esa porog qiymatlari orqali suvli piksellarni tasniflash imkonini beradi.

Suv yuzasi va suv hajmi o'rtasidagi bog'lanishni baholashda regressiya modellari keng qo'llaniladi. Ayrim tadqiqotlarda chiziqli modellar yetarli aniqlik bersa, boshqa ishlarda darajali yoki ko'phadli regressiya modellari yuqori natijalarni ko'rsatgan. Bunday modellar, ayniqsa, batimetrik o'lchashlar bilan birgalikda qo'llanilganda, suv ombori hajmini baholashda ishonchli hisoblanadi.

Shu bilan birga, Google Earth Engine platformasidan foydalangan holda suv omborlarini uzluksiz monitoring qilish bo'yicha tadqiqotlar hali yetarli darajada emas. Ayniqsa, mahalliy suv omborlari uchun suv yuzasi, suv hajmi va suv sathi o'rtasidagi bog'lanishni kompleks tahlil qilish masalasi dolzarbligini saqlab qolmoqda. Mazkur tadqiqot ushbu bo'shliqni to'ldirishga qaratilgan.

Mazkur tadqiqot obyekti sifatida O'zbekiston Respublikasi hududida joylashgan Talimarjon suv ombori tanlandi. U mamlakatning yirik gidrotexnik inshootlaridan biri bo'lib, energetika va qishloq xo'jaligini suv bilan ta'minlashda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Suv omboridagi suv sathi va hajmining o'zgarishi mavsumiy va yillik gidrologik omillar, shuningdek, inson faoliyati bilan bog'liq bo'lgan omillar ta'sirida shakllanadi.

Tadqiqotda quyidagi ma'lumotlar manbalaridan foydalanildi:

- Sentinel-1 sun'iy yo'ldoshining SAR tasvirlari (2024–2025 yillar),
- Landsat missiyasi doirasida olingan optik tasvirlar,
- suv ombori uchun 2023 va 2025 yillarda olib borilgan batimetrik o'lchashlar natijalari,
- Global Reservoir and Dam ma'lumotlar bazasidan olingan geofazoviy ma'lumotlar.

Sentinel-1 ma'lumotlari suv yuzasini aniqlashda asosiy manba sifatida qo'llanildi, chunki SAR tasvirlari bulutlilik va yorug'lik sharoitlariga bog'liq emas. Landsat tasvirlari esa qo'shimcha tekshirish va taqqoslash maqsadida foydalanildi. Batimetrik ma'lumotlar suv yuzasi va suv hajmi o'rtasidagi bog'lanishni baholashda etalon ma'lumot sifatida

xizmat qildi.

3. Tadqiqot metodologiyasi

Tadqiqot Google Earth Engine platformasining hisoblash imkoniyatlaridan foydalangan holda amalga oshirildi. Metodologiya bir nechta bosqichlarni o'z ichiga oladi: sun'iy yo'ldosh tasvirlarini tanlash va filtrlash, suv yuzasini aniqlash, vaqt qatorlarini shakllantirish hamda regressiya modellari orqali suv hajmini baholash.

Birinchi bosqichda Sentinel-1 sun'iy yo'ldoshining SAR tasvirlari tadqiqot hududi va belgilangan vaqt oralig'i bo'yicha filtrlandi. Tasvirlarni qayta ishlash jarayonida tasvir sifatini yaxshilash maqsadida median filtr qo'llanildi. Bu usul SAR tasvirlariga xos bo'lgan dog'lar shovqinini kamaytirish imkonini berdi.

Ikkinchi bosqichda suvli piksellarni aniqlash uchun orqaga tarqalish koeffitsientlari asosida porog usuli qo'llanildi. Suv yuzasi past tarqalish qiymatlari bilan xarakterlanishi hisobga olinib, belgilangan porog qiymatdan past bo'lgan piksellar suv sifatida tasniflandi. Har bir tasvir uchun suvli piksellar yig'indisi hisoblanib, suv yuzasining vaqt bo'yicha o'zgarish qatorlari shakllantirildi.

1-rasm. GEE platformasida suv ombori monitoringi

Uchinchi bosqichda suv yuzasi va suv hajmi o'rtasidagi bog'lanishni aniqlash uchun regressiya tahlili amalga oshirildi. Bu maqsadda batimetrik o'lchashlar asosida olingan suv hajmi qiymatlari suv yuzasi bilan bog'landi. Chiziqli va darajali regressiya modellari tuzilib, ularning aniqlik darajasi determinatsiya koeffitsienti orqali baholandi.

Olingan regressiya tenglamalari asosida suv yuzasining vaqt qatorlari orqali suv hajmi va suv sathi balandligining hisoblangan qiymatlari aniqlandi. Ushbu yondashuv suv omboridagi gidrologik jarayonlarni uzluksiz monitoring qilish imkonini beradi hamda an'anaviy o'lchash usullarini to'ldiruvchi samarali vosita sifatida xizmat qiladi.

Suv ombori yuzasini aniqlash Sentinel-1 sun'iy yo'ldoshining SAR tasvirlari asosida amalga oshirildi. SAR tasvirlarida suv yuzasi boshqa yer qoplamalariga nisbatan past orqaga tarqalish koeffitsientlari bilan tavsiflanadi. Shu sababli suvli hududlarni

ajratib olish uchun orqaga tarqalish qiymatlariga asoslangan porog (threshold) usulidan foydalanildi.

Har bir tasvir uchun belgilangan porog qiymatdan past bo'lgan pikselar suv sifatida tasniflandi. Natijada binar suv–quruqlik xaritalari hosil qilindi. Ushbu xaritalar asosida suvli pikselar soni hisoblandi va ularning umumiy maydoni quyidagi ifoda orqali aniqlandi:

$$A_t = N_t \cdot S_p,$$

bu yerda

- A_t — t -vaqtdagi suv yuzasining maydoni (m^2),
- N_t — suv sifatida tasniflangan pikselar soni,
- S_p — bir piksel maydoni (Sentinel-1 uchun $10\,000\ m^2$).

Har bir tasvir uchun hisoblangan suv yuzasi qiymatlari asosida suv omborining vaqt qatorlari shakllantirildi. Vaqt qatorlari suv yuzasining mavsumiy va yillik o'zgarish tendensiyalarini aniqlash imkonini berdi. Natijalarga ko'ra, suv yuzasi qiymatlarida yoz va kuz oylarida kamayish, qish va bahor oylarida esa nisbatan o'sish tendensiyasi kuzatildi. Bu holat gidrologik rejimi va suvdan foydalanish xususiyatlari bilan izohlanadi.

Suv ombori hajmini baholash uchun suv yuzasi va suv hajmi o'rtasidagi funksional bog'lanish regressiya tahlili yordamida aniqlandi. Bu maqsadda 2023 va 2025 yillarda o'tkazilgan batimetrik o'lchashlar natijalari asosida suv hajmi (V) va suv yuzasi (A) o'rtasidagi bog'lanish tahlil qilindi.

Dastlab chiziqli regressiya modeli ko'rib chiqildi:

$$V = \alpha A + \beta, \tag{1}$$

bu yerda

- V — suv hajmi (m^3),
- A — suv yuzasi maydoni (m^2),
- α, β — regressiya koeffitsientlari.

Natijalar chiziqli model suv hajmini yetarlicha aniqlikda ifodalashini ko'rsatdi va determinatsiya koeffitsienti $R^2 = 0,98$ ga teng bo'ldi. Biroq, suv ombori geometriyasining murakkabligi sababli darajali regressiya modeli yanada yuqori aniqlikni ta'minladi:

$$V = \gamma A^\delta, \tag{2}$$

bu yerda

- γ, δ — empirik regressiya koeffitsientlari.

Darajali regressiya modeli uchun determinatsiya koeffitsienti $R^2 = 0,99$ ni tashkil etdi. Bu esa suv hajmining o'zgarishini suv yuzasi orqali 99 % aniqlik bilan izohlash mumkinligini ko'rsatadi.

Shuningdek, suv yuzasi va suv sathi balandligi (H) o'rtasidagi bog'lanish ham tahlil qilindi. Ikkinchi va uchinchi tartibli regressiya modellari sinovdan o'tkazilib, eng yuqori aniqlik uchinchi tartibli modelda kuzatildi:

$$H = aA^3 + bA^2 + cA + d, \tag{3}$$

2-rasm. Suv ombori ko'rsatkichlari uchun regressiya modellari

bu yerda

- H — suv sathi balandligi (m),
- a, b, c, d — regressiya koeffitsientlari.

Mazkur model uchun determinatsiya koeffitsienti $R^2 = 0,9955$ ga teng bo'lib, suv sathi balandligini suv yuzasi orqali ishonchli baholash imkonini berdi.

Olingan regressiya tenglamalari asosida GEE platformasidan olingan suv yuzasi vaqt qatorlari yordamida 2025 yil uchun suv hajmi va suv sathi balandligining oylik qiymatlari hisoblandi. Hisoblangan natijalar suv omborining mavsumiy ish rejimini va suv resurslarining taqsimlanish xususiyatlarini chuqurroq tahlil qilish imkonini berdi.

3-rasm. Suv ombori ko'rsatkichlarining prognoz qiymatlari

4. Natijalar va muhokama

Google Earth Engine platformasi asosida olingan natijalar Talimarjon suv omborida suv yuzasining vaqt bo'yicha sezilarli o'zgarishlarga ega ekanligini ko'rsatdi. Sentinel-1 SAR tasvirlari yordamida shakllantirilgan vaqt qatorlari suv yuzasining mavsumiy dinamikasini aniqlash imkonini berdi. Kuzatuvlarga ko'ra, bahor va qish oylarida suv yuzasi maydonining nisbatan ortishi, yoz va kuz oylarida esa kamayishi qayd etildi. Bu holat daryo oqimi, bug'lanish darajasi hamda suvdan xo'jalik ehtiyojlari uchun foydalanish bilan izohlanadi.

Suv yuzasi va suv hajmi o'rtasidagi regressiya modellari tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, darajali regressiya modeli chiziqli modelga nisbatan yuqoriroq aniqlikka ega. Determinatsiya koeffitsientlarining yuqori qiymatlari ($R^2 = 0,98 - 0,99$) suv hajmining asosiy qismi suv yuzasi orqali izohlanishini tasdiqlaydi. Bu natijalar masofadan zondlash ma'lumotlari yordamida suv hajmini bilvosita baholash imkoniyati mavjudligini kўrsatadi.

Shuningdek, suv yuzasi va suv sathi balandligi o'rtasidagi bog'lanish uchun tuzilgan

regressiya modellari ham yuqori aniqlikni namoyon etdi. Uchunchi tartibli regressiya modeli suv sathi balandligini ishonchli baholash imkonini berdi ($R^2 = 0,9955$). Olingan natijalar suv omborining ish rejimini tahlil qilish va suv resurslarini boshqarish jarayonlarida muhim axborot manbai bo'lishi mumkin.

Natijalarni an'anaviy batimetrik o'lchashlar bilan taqqoslash shuni ko'rsatdiki, Google Earth Engine asosida olingan baholashlar amaliy jihatdan maqbul aniqlikka ega. Bu esa vaqt va moliyaviy xarajatlarni kamaytirgan holda suv omborlari holatini doimiy kuzatish imkonini yaratadi.

5. Xulosa

Mazkur tadqiqotda Google Earth Engine platformasi asosida suv omborlarini masofadan monitoring qilish va suv hajmini baholash usullari ishlab chiqildi. Sentinel-1 SAR va Landsat sun'iy yo'ldosh ma'lumotlari yordamida Talimarjon suv omborining suv yuzasi aniqlanib, uning vaqt bo'yicha o'zgarishlari tahlil qilindi.

Batimetrik o'lchashlar asosida suv yuzasi, suv hajmi va suv sathi balandligi o'rtasidagi bog'lanishlar regressiya modellari orqali aniqlanib, yuqori aniqlik ko'rsatkichlariga erishildi. Olingan natijalar masofadan zondlash ma'lumotlari yordamida suv omborlarining hajmiy ko'rsatkichlarini baholash mumkinligini tasdiqlaydi.

Tadqiqot natijalari suv resurslarini boshqarish, gidrotexnik inshootlar faoliyatini rejalashtirish va suv tanqisligi sharoitida qarorlar qabul qilish jarayonlarida amaliy ahamiyatga ega. Taklif etilgan yondashuv an'anaviy o'lchash usullarini to'ldiruvchi samarali vosita bo'lib, kelgusida boshqa suv omborlari uchun ham qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Adabiyotlar

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